

STATE OF THE ART AND PERFORMANCE OF THE PHOTOVOLTAIC (PV) SYSTEM FLEET IN BRUSSELS: AN ANALYSIS OF 8000 PV INSTALLATIONS

Babacar Sarr^{1*}, Jonathan Leloux¹, Gregory Neubourg², Guillaume Declève³,
Renaud Tieterickx⁴, Jonathan de Lathouwer⁴, Régis Lambert⁴

¹LuciSun, Sart-Dames-Avelines, Belgium

²Becquerel Institute, Brussels, Belgium

³SUNSET Energy, Brussels, Belgium

⁴BRUGEL, Brussels, Belgium

*Phone: +32 470 10 09 29; E-mail: babacar.sarr@lucisun.com

ABSTRACT: The photovoltaic sector is still relatively young in the world and in the Region of Brussels, where most installations are barely ten years old or less. The goal of this study is to provide an overall picture of the state of the art of the photovoltaic park in the Brussels Region. It includes an assessment of the installed equipment, the price of the installations and their performance. More than 8000 PV installations distributed across the Brussels Region were considered in this study with data available up to the end of the year 2019, and including residential and commercial PV systems. The analysis of installation prices highlights the downward trend in prices which continues in 2019 with a reduction ranging from 5% for large systems to 16% for small residential systems compared to 2018. Since 2013, the average decrease in the different installed power categories is almost 40%. The solar resource in Brussels has gradually increased over the last four decades, with an average annual horizontal global solar irradiation over the last forty years of about 1000 kWh/m². In the last ten years, the average value is estimated at 1078 kWh/m², about 8% above the average of the last four decades. A historical maximum was recorded in 2018, with 1172 kWh/m², which is about 18% higher than the average of the last four decades. The median energy yield of PV installations in the Brussels Region over the last decade was around 850 kWh/kW_p. The median Performance Ratio of the PV installations in Brussels Region during the last decade was about 65%, which can be considered as a typical and representative value of the PV park. In comparison, typical Performance Ratios in Europe are in the range of 70-80%. This study has also found a correlation between the performance of the installations and certain key parameters such as the installed peak power, the year of commissioning, the brand of photovoltaic panels, the power category or the type of owner of the installation. Comparisons between module brands have also shown that there is no clear correlation between the geographic origin of a module brand and its performance.

Keywords: Photovoltaic, PV, Performance, State of the art, Belgium, Brussels.

1 INTRODUCTION

The photovoltaic sector is still relatively young in the world and in the Region of Brussels, where most installations are barely ten years old or less. The overall level of knowledge and professionalization of the sector have been increasing over time, with the experience gained and the mistakes made, both on the part of panel and inverter manufacturers, as well as installers, public authorities or owners. The PV market is also fast evolving, and it is necessary to constantly investigate the return from the field experience and to incorporate the lessons learned into common knowledge and practise. Benchmarks and market analysis seek to understand how that PV sector is developing, and where it is going to. On the other hand, the assessment of the real energy productivity and performance of these photovoltaic installations seek to better understand the state of the art of the current installed PV fleet, its peculiarities, as well as the nature and frequency of possible problems that affect them. This better knowledge is an essential key for the proper development and sustainability of the photovoltaic subsidiary, and it helps to better guide public aid decisions.

The goal of this study is to provide an aggregate benchmark of the photovoltaic park in the Brussels Region and to provide an assessment of the installed equipment, the price of the installations and their performance. More than 8000 PV installations distributed across the Brussels Region were considered in this study with data available up to the end of the year 2019, and including residential and commercial PV systems.

2 INSTALLED PV CAPACITY

Figure 1 shows the evolution of the number of PV installations in Brussels, highly correlated to policy and financial incentives granted for the installation of PV in the Brussels Region between 2006 and 2019. For example, the initial peak in 2009 is correlated to the suspension of a regional bonus, equivalent to 50% of the investment for 2010. 2018 has seen a strong shift in terms of the number of newly installed capacity in all categories of installations. This was induced by a combination of factors, including the global equipment price drop and the development of new regional programs.

Figure 1: Evolution of number of PV installations in Brussels (2008-2019).

Figure 2 shows the evolution of the cumulative installed power of PV installations in the Brussels Region between 2008 and 2019, categorised by installed power capacity. This installed capacity has also increased over time, with a diversified size of PV installations. Small PV systems are more numerous, but large PV systems (> 250 kWp) dominate in terms of cumulative installed power since 2013 and represented in 2019 more than 50% of the total installed photovoltaic power.

Figure 2: Evolution of the cumulative installed power of PV Installations in the Brussels Region (2008-2019) categorised by Installed power capacity.

Figure 3 shows the evolution of the installed peak power in Brussels between 2007 and 2019. A noticeable trend towards higher average installed peak powers is visible.

Figure 3: Evolution of the installed peak power in Brussels between 2007 and 2019.

Normalizing the installed capacity to its surface density allows for a better comparison between Brussels

and other cities. Figure 4 shows that the Brussels Region has already installed more PV per km² than other cities analyzed, despite the higher population density (7500 inhabitants/km², which is twice as much as Liège or Antwerp). The Brussels Region shows an installed capacity of 105 W_p/inhabitant, which is slightly below the average of the other analyzed cities. The cities that performed better than Brussels either have large industrial areas (Gent, Antwerp, San Diego) or a completely different type of housing and population density (i.e. Honolulu with a density 50 times lower and mainly composed of suburban housing).

Figure 4: Comparison of the installed photovoltaic power density between Brussels and 15 other cities, in terms of kW_p/km² in 2019.

3 INSTALLATION COSTS

Figure 5 shows the evolution of the cost of installation per kW_p (€/kW_p) during the years with the highest availability of data. A clear trend towards the reduction of the cost of installations is visible for all categories of installations, and for all ranges of installed capacity.

Figure 5: Evolution of average prices of the PV installations.

4 ORIENTATION OF THE PV SYSTEMS

Figure 6 shows the distribution of the orientations of the PV systems installed in Brussels. It shows that the most frequent orientations correspond to south-south-east (-22.5°) and south-south-west (+ 22.5°). These orientations are typical of the rooftops in the city center of Brussels, where the town planning is such that very few roofs face south, and many roofs have an oblique orientation between the south-east and the south-west.

This distribution of the natural orientation of the roofs probably strongly influenced the distribution of the orientations of the photovoltaic panels installed.

Figure 6: Distribution of the orientations of the PV systems installed in Brussels.

5 SOLAR RESOURCE

Figure 7 shows the evolution of the solar resource in Brussels from over the last seven decades, as measured by a pyranometer located in Uccle and operated by Royal Meteorological Institute of Belgium (RMI). The evolution of the solar resource is evaluated through the annual value of the global horizontal irradiation (GHI).

Figure 7: Evolution of the solar resource in Brussels (1951-2018), as measured by a pyranometer located in Uccle and operated by Royal Meteorological Institute of Belgium (RMI).

The annual solar irradiation has changed significantly over the past decades, and it broke new records in Belgium in 2018, with an annual global solar irradiation in the horizontal plane of 1172 kWh/m², measured in Uccle, the headquarters of RMI. This is the highest value measured by MRI since measurements began in the 1950s. This new record only confirms the upward trends since the early 1980s, almost 4 decades. For each decade, an increase of more than 40 kWh/m² has in fact been observed, or nearly 4% per decade. The historical minimum was measured in 1981, lying just below 900 kWh/m². The average value of irradiation between 1981 and 2018 is 997 kWh/m², which can be rounded to 1000 for easier retention. This historic 2018 high is about 30% higher than the 1981 low, and about 17% higher than the average value. The average irradiation over the last decade is 1,072 kWh/m², which represents an increase of about 8% over the average of the last 40 years. As a result, most of the PV production forecasts made 10 years ago have turned out to be too pessimistic. In fact, the Belgian PV systems have produced more than expected.

The increase in solar irradiation (and therefore production) is not specific to Uccle, nor even to Belgium. Similar trends have been observed since the early 1980s in most countries in Europe and North America. The reasons for these trends are not yet fully understood. There are two main causes: the amount of aerosols in the atmosphere, and the amount of clouds, which disperse and absorb solar radiation before it reaches the ground. Recent scientific research attributes about three quarters of the trends to aerosols and one quarter to changes in cloud cover [1]. During the last decades, the Belgian sky has therefore become less loaded with aerosols, and a little less cloudy.

6 ENERGY YIELD

Figure 8 shows the distribution of the annual energy yield of the installations over the last decade. The average energy yield was 831 kWh/kW_p, and its median value is 844 kWh/kW_p, which shows a slight shift towards the lower values. The energy yields of most of the installations have values that vary between 700 and 1000 kWh/kW_p. Some installations have an energy yield of over 1100 kWh/kW_p, while others have an energy yield of less than 500 kWh/kW_p. There is a large dispersion between the highest and lowest energy yield, which may be due to differences in orientation, quality of the components and execution of the installation, as well as the presence of operational problems.

Figure 8: Distribution of yearly energy yield (2009-2019).

7 PERFORMANCE RATIO

The performance Ratio (PR) has been used to analyze the overall performance of the installations. The PR is defined as:

$$PR = \frac{Y_f}{Y_r}$$

where the final yield Y_f is defined by E_{pv}/P^{STC} , and the reference yield Y_r is defined by G_{TI}/G^{STC} , where: E_{pv} is the net electrical energy produced by the installation during a given period, P^{STC} is the rated power of the PV generator under Standard Test Conditions (STC), G^{STC} is the global solar irradiance under STC (i.e., 1000 W/m²), and G_{TI} is the Global Tilted Irradiation received by the PV generator.

Figure 9 shows the distribution of the annual Performance Ratio of all the PV installations analysed in

the database and for the years 2009 to 2019. It therefore provides a global picture of the typical performance of the PV installations in Brussels.

Figure 9: Distribution of the annual Performance Ratio of all the PV installations analysed in the database (2009-2019).

The distribution curve that best explains the distribution of the Performance Ratio in Brussels is a Weibull type distribution. This is an asymmetric distribution that is often observed when a population has a physical boundary at one of its extremes but not at the other. In the case of photovoltaic installations in Belgium, it is generally physically very unlikely to be able to obtain an annual PR value greater than 90%, because certain losses in the system are often present, whereas it is more frequent that installations have significantly lower PRs than average, primarily due to performance issues. The Weibull distribution suggests that the most typical value of PR to retain for a photovoltaic installation installed in Brussels during the last ten years is between 65% and 70%. A significant variation is observed around this typical value, with 90% for the best installations and 40% for the worst performers. This is a very large disparity which can be explained by a not insignificant proportion of installations suffering from undetected and/or untreated performance problems.

These typical annual PR values of 65-70% which characterize photovoltaic installations in Brussels can be compared to the PR values obtained in other studies carried out in Belgium or elsewhere in Europe. Some studies have evaluated the PR of tens of thousands of installations in Europe, whose years of commissioning are generally representative of the installed PV park in Brussels. A study of more than 31,000 photovoltaic installations in Europe located in Belgium, France, Italy, Luxembourg, Germany and the Netherlands concluded that the average PRs are between 70% and 75% [2]. Another study covering more than 31,000 photovoltaic installations in Europe mainly located in Belgium, France and the United Kingdom concluded that the PR of most installations is between 60% and 90%, with average values per country typically above 75%, and typical PR values around 80% [3]. A study of a thousand photovoltaic installations in Wallonia obtained very similar conclusions, with an average value of 78%, and a typical value of around 80% [4]. PR values in Wallonia are therefore, on average, around 5-10% higher than in BCR. Several causes can explain these differences. In Wallonia, photovoltaic panels are often installed on the roofs of houses that are relatively free of shading, while

in a dense urban context such as that of Brussels, the panels are often much more affected by the shading. Differences in installation and maintenance practices may also be the cause of these observed performance differences. However, given the significant difference in the performance observed in Wallonia and in Brussels, it would be interesting to study the Brussels stock in more depth to try to better understand the reasons for these relatively low PR values and to remedy them as much as possible, for the installations of the current PV park but also and especially for the installations to come.

Figure 10 shows the distribution of the monthly Performance Ratio for the reference year 2018. It can be seen that the dispersion of the performance ratio values is larger than for the annual performance ratio. This can be explained by several factors. Firstly, the monthly variability of performance is greater than the annual variability because operating conditions (irradiation, temperature, shading, etc.) can vary greatly depending on the month of the year. Secondly, operating problems and failures can affect PV installations for one or more months before being resolved. This strong dispersion of the PR is an indication that many installations underperform strongly during at least a certain period of the year.

Figure 10: Distribution of monthly Performance Ratio for the reference year 2018.

Figure 11 shows the monthly evolution of the Performance Ratio during the reference year 2018. It can be seen that the PR values tend to be slightly higher during spring and summer than during autumn and winter. This means that the PR is higher when the sun is higher in the sky, which suggests that many installations are affected by strong shading during winter. These changes in PR can also be explained by other factors, including poor performance of installations under low irradiance conditions. This situation can occur when the inverters are oversized, which seems to be the case in Brussels for many of the installations. This evolution of monthly PR values with higher values in summer than in winter is characteristic of photovoltaic installations in dense urban areas. In large solar power plants, an opposite evolution is often observed during the months of the year with summer PR values slightly lower than winter values due to the thermal losses of the PV panels.

Figure 15: Relationship between the specific power of photovoltaic panels and the Performance Ratio of the installations.

Figure 16 illustrates the relationship between the Performance Ratio of a photovoltaic installation and its cost. As discussed earlier, the prices of PV installations have fallen sharply over the past ten years, and they also tend to be lower when the installation is larger. To allow for valid comparisons, the analyses were therefore limited to installations commissioned in 2018 and whose peak power is between 3 kW_p and 10 kW_p. These comparisons show that the correlation between the cost of an installation and its energy performance is generally very low. However, there is a slightly positive correlation between cost and performance, which suggests that there is some justification for the existence of price differentiation in the market. However, the low degree of general correlation shows that it is still very difficult to understand the pricing mechanisms on the current market. If the price/quality ratio does not seem to be the main factor that dictates these prices, other more important parameters could explain it. This is particularly the case with the degree of difficulty of the realization of photovoltaic installations in the urban context of Brussels.

Figure 16: Relationship between the Performance Ratio of a photovoltaic installation and its cost.

8 CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of installation prices highlights the downward trend in prices which continues in 2019 with a reduction ranging from 5% for large systems to 16% for small residential systems compared to 2018. Since 2013, the average decrease in the different installed power categories is almost 40%. The solar resource in Brussels

has gradually increased over the last four decades, with an average annual horizontal global solar irradiation over the last forty years of about 1000 kWh/m². In the last ten years, the average value is estimated at 1078 kWh/m², about 8% above the average of the last four decades. A historical maximum was recorded in 2018, with 1172 kWh/m², which is about 18% higher than the average of the last four decades. The median energy yield of PV installations in the Brussels Region over the last decade was around 850 kWh/kW_p. The median Performance Ratio of the PV installations in Brussels Region during the last decade was about 65%, which can be considered as a typical and representative value of the PV park. In comparison, typical Performance Ratios in Europe are in the range of 70-80%. This study has also found a correlation between the performance of the installations and certain key parameters such as the installed peak power, the year of commissioning, the brand of photovoltaic panels, the power category or the type of owner of the installation. Comparisons between module brands have also shown that there is no clear correlation between the geographic origin of a module brand and its performance.

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